

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL PROBLEMS OF THE LEGAL STATUS OF COMMERCIALY CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION

Raimova Nargiza Doroyevna

Doctor of Sciences in Law

Professor of the International Private Law and Civil Law Department

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

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Annotation: Information, exactly confidential information, is the most important component of the development of society in formative modern world. The current civil society is gradually turning from an informed to the information, so we can fearlessly say that the 21th century is considered to be the age of information. Information is a very important and necessary element of any activity of man, society and the state in the public, social-economic and political spheres.

It is noted in the article that the problems related to the fact that the legislation provides a wide range of powers by government organs in the different tests that may affect the interests of sensitive enterprise because unset concrete facets of government intervention in economic activities of enterprises considered painful for entrepreneurs in many countries.

Key words: intellectual property, information, confidential information, legal regime, types of information, methods of protection of information, modern criteria.

In modern conditions information is a special kind of commodity, which has a certain value. In this regard, one cannot but agree with the opinion of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, who states that “improvement of the system of ensuring information security and information protection, timely and adequate counteraction to threats in the information sphere are priority directions in the sphere of ensuring security” [3].

For entrepreneurs, the most valuable information is often that which they use to achieve the goals of their enterprise and the disclosure of which may deprive them of the opportunity to realize these goals, i.e. creates threats to the security of entrepreneurial activity. Of course, not all information can, in case of its disclosure, create various threats, but there are some types of information, in particular, commercial and banking secrets, which need to be protected [16, 21-26].

As rightly notes K.S.Kushiyeu, “the institute of trade secrets is one of the important components of the system of ensuring the stability of the market, limitation of monopolism in production and economic relations and through these factors to a certain extent influences the block of social relations in general. Without detailed development of the legal institute of trade secrets it is practically impossible to progressive development of healthy market relations, as well as full provision of the rights of authors of discoveries and inventions” [11, 116-119].

The study of the issues of formation and development of the legal institute of trade secrets, determination of its place and role in the formation of mechanisms of information support for the activities of commercial organizations and the legal provision of their information security is currently an independent theoretical task, the establishment and fundamental importance of which involves attracting the attention of civil science [14, 19-20].

Thus, when studying the nature of trade secrets, first of all, in our opinion, it is necessary to understand what is its place among the objects of civil rights, in particular, in the system of intellectual property objects, because, as rightly notes Gafurov A., “in modern conditions, intellectual property right is becoming one of the important factors determining the position of the country in the world. At the same time, solving the problems of intellectual property protection is an extremely difficult task. This is due to the insufficient development of legal norms, differences in the approaches of individual countries and groups of countries, lack of cross-border structures for the enforcement of laws” [4, 18].

Before answering the question whether trade secrets can be considered as intellectual property, it is necessary to understand what the concept of “intellectual property” is.

The term “intellectual property” can be found for the first time in the French legislation of the XVIII century. Its justification is contained within the doctrine of natural law, presented by French philosophers-enlighteners: Voltaire, Diderot, Rousseau and others. In accordance with their views, “the right of the creator of a creative result, be it a literary work or an invention, is his inalienable, natural right, arises from the very nature of creative activity and exists independently of the recognition of this right by the state power” [18, 626].

The theory opposing the proprietary one is the increasingly recognized theory of exclusive rights. In accordance with the main provisions of this theory, the rights of authors, inventors, patentees, etc. should be recognized as rights of

a special kind, which are outside the classical division of civil rights into proprietary, obligatory and personal rights [6, 266].

The concept of “result of intellectual activity” is detailed in the legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan devoted to the regulation of relations related to specific objects of intellectual property. Thus, for example, in accordance with the Copyright and Related Rights Act, the object of copyright is works of science, literature and art that are the result of creative activity [1].

Meanwhile, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Article 1031 defines the object of intellectual property as “the result of intellectual activity” and not as “the result of creative activity” [2]. The concept of intellectual activity is broader than the concept of creative activity and may well include non-creative objects.

Further, the literature indicates that the object of intellectual property in all cases refers to an intangible good that is merely embodied in certain tangible objects that are its material carriers [18, 620].

Thus, the object of intellectual property is a certain intangible good created as a result of human intellectual activity. It can also be information. As already noted, information itself is intangible and is only embodied on material carriers.

Also quite fair is the point of view of V.A.Kopylov, who believes that “information is created practically in the process of any intellectual (mental) activity of a person” [10, 49].

Accordingly, a trade secret as a type of information may well be considered an object of intellectual property.

The question, however, is whether it actually is one?

In foreign literature, for example, the issue of attributing trade secrets to intellectual property objects is solved in different ways. Thus, the American author Richard Stim writes: “Trade secrets are an important type of intellectual property rights” [20, 236].

In Germany, on the contrary, such information is not referred to the objects of exclusive rights. Thus, according to G.Stumpf, “know-how is not a form of industrial property protection, as it does not have the characteristics of an exclusive right” [23, 33].

Another scholar of German intellectual property law also notes: “There is neither an absolute nor an exclusive right to know-how for intangible results of intellectual activity” [8, 15-16].

The attribution of trade secrets to intellectual property is due to the fact that historically the birth of the institution of trade secrets took place within the framework of such an object of civil rights as intellectual property, and its legal regulation was built on a model as close as possible to the already known one [7, 99-113].

Proponents of the first approach, in particular, A.P.Sergeyev, V.A.Dozorov, believe that the information constituting a trade secret should be considered an object of intellectual property, as it has all its properties and is a type of intellectual property. For example, A.P.Sergeyev notes that “trade secret is an institution of intellectual property, it has all the properties of an object of intellectual property” [18, 620]. A.A.Fatyanov adheres to a similar point of view [21, 284].

V.A.Dozorov points out that “for isolated information, which is understood as special information that has commercial value and is not publicly available, it is necessary to fix an absolute right. Since the information represents intangible knowledge, they are assigned the rights attributed to the number of exclusive rights. However, these are not traditional exclusive rights, but rather peculiar” [7, 99-113].

V.Smirnov argues that “trade secret is not an independent object of civil rights, it can be attributed to the result of intellectual activity. He confirms the similarity of these concepts, comparing the following features: both these objects are intangible, they arise as a result of intellectual activity, although the creative level of these objects may not be comparable, the criteria of negotiability and protectability are applicable to these objects” [19, 34-37].

E.V.Shishmareva adheres to a broad approach to the understanding of intellectual activity, that is, when intellectual property law regulates a wide range of property (exclusive) and related personal non-property relations arising from the results of intellectual activity and equivalent means of individualization of a legal entity, individualization of products, works and services. In this regard, it is pointed out that a trade secret is recognized as a result of intellectual activity [22, 340].

Severin R.V. believes that “trade secret, which combines the secret of production (know-how) and commercial information, refers to ‘non-traditional’ objects of intellectual property. In support of this conclusion, he points out that trade secrets are the result of intellectual activity, which is a sign of intellectual property” [17, 29].

In contrast to the above authors, the proponent of the opposite approach, in particular, the Russian legal scholar O.A.Gorodov, believes that “the legal regime of secret information is fundamentally different from the legal regime established in respect of protected results of intellectual activity”.

In his view, this distinction is manifested in the following:

1. In the opposite orientation of the interests of the owner of confidential information and the interests of the owner of information representing the result of intellectual activity, since the persons of the first category are interested in taking measures to prevent the dissemination of relevant information, and the second, on the contrary, are interested in the dissemination of the intellectual product.

2. In different legal mechanisms of protection of the rights and interests of the owner of the result of intellectual activity and the owner of trade secrets. The owner of information constituting a trade secret restricts its dissemination by technical and other means. Here there is a variant of the mechanism of information protection alternative to the exclusive right - de facto monopoly.

Deliberately concealed information cannot be included in the framework of exclusive rights, because the factor of their unknown nature does not allow to establish the very content of information as an object of protection. In this case, it is impossible, as is the case with the results of intellectual activity, to determine the actions that can be performed by the owner of the information himself and to authorize to perform [5, 82].

Kolomiyets A.V. also believes that “trade secret is an independent object of civil rights and does not refer to a type of intellectual activity” [9, 62].

Belarusian scientist Losev S.S., in turn, also points out that “undisclosed information (in particular, trade secrets) does not refer to the objects of intellectual property”. The opinion on attributing trade secrets to the objects of exclusive right, according to Losev S.S., is contradictory, “since the monopoly granted to the owner of the exclusive right presupposes to determine the positive component of the right to information, and this is impossible to do” [12, 62].

As far as the Republic of Uzbekistan is concerned, our national legislation and scientific literature currently reflect the approach that trade secrets relate to intellectual property, as civil legislation defines information constituting a trade secret as a form of protection of undisclosed information, which, in turn, is an object of intellectual property rights. This follows from the provisions of

Chapter 64 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Protection of undisclosed information from unlawful use” [2].

A similar approach is reflected in the works of our scientists. For example, Okyulov O. [13, 170], I.Rustambekov, A.Nuridullayev [15, 4] also believe that trade secrets, including know-how, are included in the system of intellectual property objects.

Based on the above, we have come to the conclusion that trade secrets have a dual nature. On the one hand, in our opinion, just like intellectual property objects, information constituting a trade secret arises as a result of intellectual activity. But, on the other hand, we believe that, to date, certain differences exist between trade secrets and intellectual property objects, which lie in the mechanism and purposes of their protection. Intellectual property objects are open to third parties and are often valuable precisely because of their wide distribution (e.g., copyright, patent right, trademark, service mark, etc.), while information constituting a trade secret is valuable to its owner only when it is unknown to third parties and, accordingly, hidden from them.

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